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Mettl7a functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Mettl7a as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo. In contrast, Ythdf2 was not affected by TE commitment.

Citations

1. Constantinou, M., Nicholson, J., Zhang, X., Maniati, E., Lucchini, S., Rosser, G., Vinel, C., Wang, J., Lim, Y.M., Brandner, S. and Nelander, S., 2024. Lineage specification in glioblastoma is regulated by METTL7B. Cell Reports, 43(6).